

THE USAGE OF ICT IN THE FORMATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ESP STUDENTS

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Annotation. This article is given instructive and systemic parts involving data advancements for the improvement of foreign language open ability and surveying the level of its development among learners. The point of the review was to decide the educational circumstances for the utilization of the video conferencing mode as one of the systemic devices to work on the viability of showing foreign languages at the college, coordinated both full-time and distance. The vitally exact exploration technique was trial preparing, the assessment of the aftereffects of which was done based on uncommonly created models. The review showed the high pedantic capability of this sort of current data innovation, like video gatherings with local speakers of a foreign language, which can be acknowledged with equipped systemic help, including fundamental preparation, planning, and intensive investigation of all viewpoints and phases of the example. Simultaneously, the coordinating and planning activities as an educator mediator of instructive exercises in the example is important. Appraisal of learners' discourse abilities ought to be led as per clear models. Dependent upon the distinguished pedantic circumstances, the instructive interaction is enhanced with new hierarchical structures, the mental freedom of learners is created, mental interest is invigorated, and positive inspiration for learning a foreign language is expanded.

Keywords: Information technology, video conference, distance learning, interactive educational environment, interactive cooperation, communicative competence, foreign languages.

Introduction. At present, because of the gamble of different crises, preparing at all levels ought to be prepared whenever to change to a removed configuration, without losing its viability, which can be accomplished using current data innovations. It ought to be noticed that distance learning can satisfactorily contend with conventional full-time types of instruction while enjoying specific benefits that should be effectively brought into the instructive interaction. Under the expression "distance learning" we comprehend an innovation for coordinating the instructive cycle, which is done chiefly with the utilization of data and telecom innovations in the intuitive collaboration of far-off members through open access stations (predominantly using the Web).[]

Present-day methods for correspondence work with the foundation of remote contact between members in the instructive cycle, and joint media transmission

projects help to uncover the capacities of learners, staying away from the deficiencies of conventional gathering work and ensuring individualization of preparation. These days, data advances are generally utilized in the act of showing foreign languages, permitting more a productive association with the instructive cycle, further developing the foreign language open capability of learners, fostering their mental freedom, as well as giving distance learning. We consider informative capability as the capacity to do discourse movement through the concentration on language as per the objectives and circumstances of correspondence inside the structure of a specific field of action. The premise of informative capability is language information, discourse abilities, and capacities, as well as the capability of the person to further develop the framed open abilities autonomously.

The training-focused model of schooling characterizes foreign language open capability as the amount of information, and abilities, yet additionally as the singular's capacity to realize the potential obtained in the educational experience. In this manner, the actual idea of "capability" in the system of foreign language open ability is deciphered as construction that mirrors the collaboration of mental and powerful abilities, the presence of inspiration, and important worth directions. At the end of the day, the parts of open capability are a blend of inward and outside parts of an individual's informative action. At the current phase of the advancement of schooling, the compelling arrangement of open ability as the objective of showing foreign languages is accomplished using different data innovations, media instructive projects, bona fide sound and video materials that can tackle the issue of absence of discourse practice, increase the instructive interaction and carry it nearer to genuine circumstances of foreign language correspondence.

The viability of involving sound and video materials in the instructive cycle is certain, yet they permit learners to act for the most part as beneficiaries of the foreign language discourse, even though they permit the production of a discourse circumstance in the classroom. Notwithstanding, the instructive discourse circumstance can't supplant the genuine correspondence circumstance. In this way, as we would see it, one of the best approaches to sorting out the most common way of showing a foreign language utilizing data innovation is to utilize the video gathering mode with local speakers of the concentrated language. Video gathering is an area of data innovation that gives synchronous two-way transmission of intuitive data a good way off progressively. Video gathering permits you to coordinate a discussion of at least two people, whose members are taken out from one another and impart

utilizing webcams.

Video gathering with local speakers permits you to foster the immediacy of unfamiliar discourse, trains you to perceive non-verbal methods for correspondence like looks and signals, and acquaints you with the way of life of correspondence and the style of connections in the nation of the language being contemplated. It alludes to such data innovations that make a virtual phonetic and social space, work with the trade between delegates of various etymological social orders. Considering the lingua-didactic capability of video gathering, it ought to be noticed that it empowers virtual drenching in a legitimate climate of the working of the language and culture, intelligent participation with their genuine speakers, making the circumstances for an unfamiliar language polylogue. Individualization is of specific significance in working on the different parts of open skill, because, contingent upon the by and by huge subjects of the learners and the reason for the example, the understudy etymologist leads a discussion with local speakers of the language he is considering, pointed toward further developing whether his semantic, sociolinguistic, social or phonetic and discourse capability. []

The point of the review was to decide the instructional circumstances for the utilization of the video meeting mode as one of the systemic devices for the arrangement of the open capability of learners, as well as to distinguish the adequacy of the thought about the type of intelligent collaboration during the time spent showing foreign languages. The super observational technique for research was the trial instructing of the French language utilizing the video conferencing mode, directed by us based on the Kazan Government College. The subjects of the video meeting are the issues of the current youth. Learning results were assessed in light of exceptionally planned rules. An examination of coordinated learning permitted us to reach determinations about its viability and legitimize instructive circumstances, the recognition of which permits us to involve the considered assortment of data innovations to shape the informative skill of learners with full-time and distance learning of foreign languages. The accessibility of a PC class with Web access and furnishing PCs with a webcam and mouthpiece is the fundamental gear for classroom work.

Among an extensive variety of programming, one of the most reasonable ones is Skype. Video correspondence can be coordinated with different local speakers, yet the best, as we would like to think, is the association of joint classes with unfamiliar instructors and companions of learners, which permits us to settle a more extensive scope of pedantic errands. We offer a depiction of one of our classes with the support of French speakers, which was coordinated by video

meeting. Before the example, the learners rehashed the topical jargon under the direction of a vital, introduced the unknown lexical instructor, if important, acquainted the obscure lexical units with them. It is critical to set up learners for dynamic correspondence, inspire them to clarify some things, and offer their answers to the issues talked about. Reviewing the decorum of discourse behavior will be helpful. The illustration started with a show by the video meeting members, trailed by a little discourse of the francophone member, during which he momentarily covered the discussion.

Such starter listening is intended to help tune into the most common way of seeing the discourse of local speakers since the instructor when in doubt, has more clear and more estimated elocution and less maltreatment of everyday articulations and language, normal for youngsters. The discourse of a local speaker may at first be significantly more challenging to comprehend because of the above reasons. This reality by and by affirms the worth of these kinds of exercises, as they give a chance to gain proficiency with a vivacious current language of correspondence, and not just expert its scholarly structure. Then, individual smaller-than-usual discussions (for a few minutes) were coordinated for every understudy with local French speakers. During this discussion, questions were asked regarding the subject of the example. In the following phase of the example, the drive was given by the actual students, who had the option to talk about different parts of the issue viable.

The conversation can be coordinated in the organization of a “round table”, where learners alternate reserve the option to talk and pose inquiries of interest. Toward the finish of the example summing up the conversation subject. Every understudy had the amazing chance to offer their viewpoint and express their perspective on the issue viable. A foreign language educator can take a negligible part in the discussion, yet entirely should continually screen learners' considerations and keep up with their movement. Simultaneously, he has the amazing chance to assess the understudy's discourse abilities by specific boundaries.[] Among the primary boundaries for evaluating the abilities of verbal correspondence in French during the testing system, we utilized the accompanying models: regulating articulation, dynamic cooperation in the exchange, information on jargon and effective data, the arrangement of morphological also, syntactic abilities. Allow us to consider in subtleties the measures for surveying unfamiliar open skills utilized during the examination.

Conclusion. Language is a forever evolving structure, hence, the types of its review and control should be all the while and ideally changed. At the current phase of specialized improvement, an ever-increasing number of chances are

opening okay to working on the most common way of shaping foreign language informative capability and uncovering the level of its arrangement. The intelligent instructive climate enjoys a few benefits because of its dialogical nature, movement inventive nature, giving the chance of free navigation, support for the individual turn of events, and participation. Intuitive participation of members in the instructive cycle ought to be incorporated considering individual attributes, needs, and thought processes of learners, given shared understanding, and the advancement of compassion.

This will guarantee the making of agreeable circumstances for dominating a foreign language, in which learners will feel their prosperity and scholarly practicality. As a general rule, inventive data innovations make it conceivable to guarantee that the language and discourse preparation of learners is steady with the social request of society for an extensively evolved individual with sociocultural, intercultural, etymological, and discourse skills. New types of association of the instructive interaction add to its strengthening by animating mental movement, which at last prompts expanded learning proficiency.

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